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The Landing Obligation in EU Demersal fisheries in the Mediterranean, Western waters and the North Sea – status, approaches and looking ahead towards the next CFP reform

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Executive Summary

This Policy Brief provides an overview of the current status, initial experiences, barriers, and opportunities with regard to applying the LO in mixed demersal fisheries in the North Sea, North Western Waters and South Western Waters, the Mediterranean and the Azores. This area covers the all DiscardLess case studies, including the North Sea/West of Scotland, Celtic Sea, Eastern Channel & Bay of Biscay, the western and eastern Mediterranean, and the Azores. In quota managed fisheries, Mixed demersal fisheries provide the biggest challenge for implementation of the LO due to the difficulty of matching quotas with catches for multiple species which are caught simultaneously but in varying proportions.

The policy brief reviews where we are with the LO now and what the main issues are. The main orientation of the policy brief is forward looking: what do stakeholders and researchers consider as the main approaches are to deal with the issues in each region until the next CFP reform? To conclude, we take a longer perspective, providing suggestions for how to implement a workable discard policy with the next reform of the CFP.

The Policy Brief is written for policy makers, the fishing industry, NGO's and citizens with an interest in fisheries management and is based on policy documents, stakeholder interviews, meetings and literature.

Box 1: Report Highlights

- Implementation of the LO is occurring across all DiscardLess case studies with measures such as trials of selective gears, provision of information on implementation requirements and the use of exemptions among the aspects most evident.
- There is very little evidence to date of changes in discard rates or fishing practices although that is not confirmation that these are not occurring but reflects a lack of data to draw such conclusions at present.
- Recording of discards under exemptions and unwanted catches remains lower than expected although there is evidence of some increase in these practices in early 2019.
- It is difficult to assess whether changes in fishing practices to promote selectivity and avoid discards are taking place. Given some delays in sanctioning and gradual uptake of new gears (e.g. for trawlers catching Baltic Cod), recent changes to permitted gears (e.g. new mesh size and TCM requirements in the Celtic Sea) and the upcoming implementation of the new Technical Measures framework some improvements in selectivity and discard rates would be expected.
- The quality of discard data is not improving due to industry fears about the potential negative impact of providing discard data and subsequent decrease in observer coverage in some Member States. Stakeholders across all backgrounds have expressed concerns about the risks associated with potential rises in fishing mortality.
- Concerns about efficient and effective monitoring of the LO are increasingly being channeled into calls for electronic monitoring across all fleets or on a risk assessment basis. These calls are particularly strong in some MS such as Denmark.
- A move towards a Results Based Management approach involving electronic monitoring is being advocated with some industry stakeholders specifying that it would require changes to the LO in order for it to gain industry support.
- Despite a general negative attitude towards the LO among fishers contributions to the final DiscardLess conference in January 2019 including from fishers outlined both positives, such as the incentivising of change, as well as implementation barriers. These are described in greater detail in Section 8.2 below.

Box 2: The methods/approaches followed

- Interviews with a broad range of stakeholders from Commission level, through national administrators, industry and NGO representatives and individual fishermen.
- Participation in relevant national, regional and EU meetings.
- Analysis of relevant policy statements, regulatory documents and academic literature.

Box 3: How these results can be used and by who?

- The policy brief on guidelines for the implementation of the discard policy in European regions is of interest to stakeholders at all levels in EU fisheries as the question of what is actually happening with the LO in other fisheries and regions is asked regularly.

Box 4: Policy Recommendations

- Data shortfalls make it difficult to make a reliable assessment of the extent of LO implementation and its impact. Improvements in the following areas of data provision would greatly assist with this assessment process.
- Recording of discards and unwanted catches at vessel level is poor across all case studies and has been identified by STECF as the most significant problem with monitoring LO implementation. MS will have to develop stronger accounting measures based on last haul analysis if this trend continues.
- As part of annual reporting on LO implementation MS should provide data not just on selectivity trials undertaken but also on the uptake rates for the use of such gears beyond trial situations. This would allow assessments of changes in selectivity patterns within fisheries to be made.
- The uptake rates of selective gears could be potentially accelerated by incentivising their use with additional quota.
- Negative industry attitudes towards the LO across all case studies point to the necessity to find workable discard reduction plans at regional level. The evolving regionalisation process which now incorporates technical measures, multi-annual plans, discard plans and in some cases bycatch reduction plans may provide the necessary framework to overcome industry fears particularly regarding choke closures.
- Reduced uncertainty regarding the use of measures such as inter-species flexibility and its effect on relative stability would assist with mitigating potential chokes.
- The need for effective monitoring and control of the LO is clear. Calls for the use of electronic monitoring as the solution will also require some degree of industry acceptance in order for this to be viable. Implementing an electronic monitoring approach either on a risk basis or as part of a wider results-based management approach could make this a more feasible option.

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Glossary

AC: Advisory Council

CMT: Choke Mitigation Tool

EFCA: European Fisheries Control Agency

EM: Electronic Monitoring

IQF: Inter-species Quota Flexibility

JR: Joint Recommendation

LO: Landing Obligation

MAP: Multi-Annual Management Plans

MC: Monitoring and Control

MS: Member State

NSAC: North Sea Advisory Council

NWWAC: North Western Waters Advisory Council

RBM: Results-Based Management

STECF: Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries

SWWAC: South Western Waters Advisory Council

1. Purpose and Scope of the Policy Brief

This fourth and final DiscardLess Policy Brief provides an overview of the current status, barriers, and opportunities with regard to applying the Landing Obligation (LO) in the regions and fisheries that constitute DiscardLess case studies, and where the Landing Obligation applies.²

The policy brief has a focus on policy implementation and governance, and provides a complementary perspective to the technical and tactical level recommendations on Discard Mitigation Strategies offered in DiscardLess deliverable D7.6. Based on a short review of the context of the LO in the case studies, the Policy brief identifies steps that could be taken to improve implementation of the LO as it is currently framed. In the final section, the Policy brief considers what changes could be made to improve the discard policy of the CFP in the longer term to improve discard rates and to support the best use of unwanted catches. The long term considerations are directed at the next CFP reform.

These case studies addressed include the mixed demersal fisheries in the North Sea and West of Scotland, North Western Waters (i.e. the Celtic Sea), South Western Waters (i.e. the Azores) and the Mediterranean fisheries. This excludes the case of Baltic and Pelagic fisheries. These were the first fisheries that the LO was applied to in 2015, and these were addressed in the first policy brief of the DiscardLess project (Fitzpatrick and Nielsen, 2016). This policy brief will only provide a brief update on issues relating to the application of the LO in demersal fisheries in the Baltic.

The key questions addressed in each of the DiscardLess case study regions are:

- What is the status of LO implementation?
- Have there been any changes reported in discard rates?
- Have there been any reported landings of unwanted catch?
- What approaches have been adopted in the region? Such approaches could include management or policy measures such as the use of closed areas, more selective gear, quota swaps or changes in quota management
- How have these approaches contributed to LO implementation?
- Are there measures which have worked better than others or are there any positive developments which could provide building blocks for the future? What are the outstanding issues or what LO implementation barriers are there?

Information sources for the policy brief include research done in case studies across all work packages by DiscardLess partners, various reports on LO implementation from MSs, ACs and the European Parliament, Advisory Council advice and meeting reports, selected

² Policy brief number 1 (D7.1) covered the first 12 months of the LO in Baltic and pelagic fisheries. Policy brief number 2 (D7.2) looked ahead at the main issues facing Mediterranean fisheries in advance of the implementation of the LO there and made some relevant policy recommendations. Policy brief number 3 (D7.5) addressed experiences with implementation of the Landing Obligation in mixed demersal fisheries in the North Sea, North Western and South Western waters.

chapters from a recently published book on the LO (Uhlmann et al., 2019), feedback from the final DiscardLess conference and interviews with key actors.

The Policy Brief is written for policy makers, the fishing industry, NGO's and citizens with an interest in fisheries management and is based on policy documents, stakeholder interviews, meetings and literature.

2. Key elements of the LO for mixed demersal fisheries

Scope: The LO was phased in from 2015 to 2019. From 1st of January 2019, the LO reached its full scope and applies to all catches of species subjected to Total Allowable Catch (TAC) limits or, in the Mediterranean, to a minimum landing size (MLS).

Governance context: The main participants in developing recommendations for discard plans and implementing the Commission regulations are the Member State High Level Groups (HLG) and the Advisory Councils (AC). The HLGs are made up of fisheries administrators from the member states in those regional seas and make Joint Recommendations (JR) for discard plans following consultation with the ACs. The ACs are the main forum for representation of interest groups (mainly fishing industry and environmental NGOs), and advise the European Commission and Member States on the management of fisheries in their regional seas.

Minimum Conservation Reference Size (MCRS): The LO requires that fish under the MCRS are landed but prohibits their use for direct human consumption. Catches of all fish, including fish below the MCRS must be recorded and counted against quotas.

Exemptions: Species and fisheries can be exempted based on evidence of high survival rates for discarded fish. Further, up to 5% of the total catch of a species may be discarded if it is shown that selectivity increases are difficult to achieve or that handling of unwanted catches is overly costly (*de minimis* exemptions).

Discard plans: In the absence of multiannual plans groups of member states organised at a regional level develop discard plans in consultation with advisory councils. These plans are submitted as "joint recommendations", which detail the species to be included in the LO, at which times and also any exemptions. Following review of the joint recommendations by the Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) the plans are adopted by the European Commission either in full or with amendments.

19 Regional Discard Plans have been adopted the Commission following Joint Recommendations from regional groups of member states in the EU since 2014. The Discard plans have defined Calendar of implementation for species and fisheries, defined the Commission following Joint Recommendations Minimum Conservation reference Sizes (MCRS) and applicable exemptions in terms of high survivability and *de minimis*). From the 1st of January 2019, the LO reached its full scope of application in terms of areas and species, and it now applies to all species with TAC or a minimum size limit.

Quota flexibility: The LO requires that fishermen have access to quotas to cover their catches or they have to cease fishing (see "choke species problem" below). Accordingly, there are rules that allow for some conditional transfer of quota between years and between species.

Choke species: The most pressing and significant issue facing LO implementation in mixed fisheries is undoubtedly the problem of dealing with choke situations and the potential negative effects on fishing fleets.

What is a choke species?

“A choke species is a species for which the available quota is exhausted (long) before the quotas are exhausted of (some of) the other species that are caught together in a (mixed) fishery” (Zimmermann et. al 2016).

3. The LO in the North Sea case study

There have not been any reported changes in discard rates for fisheries in the North Sea and West of Scotland case studies and likewise there have been very little reported landings of unwanted catches. MS reports from the region indicate that reporting of catches discarded under exemptions remains highly variable and landings of fish below MCRS are well below levels that would be expected based on previous data (STECF, 2018). There is little change observed in fishing practices to avoid unwanted catch of under MCRS fish.

Changes to fishing practices in order to avoid unwanted catches have been reported in the North Sea but uptake of selective gears by industry has been low.

Trials of control and monitoring tools including cameras have continued but they have only been used in experimental settings and are not used in non-trial fishing operations.

A recent NSAC document describes the science and observer situation as one where there is “degradation of catch data as the distinction between scientific observers and enforcement is blurred by the implementation of the landing obligation” (NSAC, 2019).

MS in their reports to the Commission have repeatedly raised the issue of ensuring a level playing field (STECF, 2018). They are concerned that it may be disadvantageous to their fleets to use a strict control system if other competing fleets are not doing so.

The Scheveningen group and the NSAC have conducted extensive analysis of which species are likely to create the greatest choke problems and also how these choke problems may best be addressed.

Interviews with individuals involved in North Sea fisheries management indicate that there are concerns that fishing mortality on some species may be rising due to the fact that quotas are now allocated on a catch rather than landings basis while discarding patterns appear to be unchanged.

In Denmark in particular, and the UK to a certain extent, there is an emphasis across many of the participants in fisheries management on much stronger catch accounting and documentation practices involving electronic monitoring (EM) and enhanced last haul analysis programs.

It is felt that such programs will create a pressure within MS on vessel operators to fully account for their catches and reduce fishing pressure on vulnerable stocks. One viewpoint expressed was that vessels in receipt of EMFF funding should be under additional pressure to provide documentation of discard rates.

A document produced to indicate the priorities for the Danish presidency of the Scheveningen Group (2019) highlights the choke problem and indicates their desire to revisit swapping practices between Member States in 2019. The document also stresses the importance of FDF, to be achieved through EM.

The European Commission in a response to a NSAC communication on TAC and quota based options for addressing the challenges of the LO (NSAC, 2018) states that “One of

the key tools provided by the Basic Regulation concerning the landing obligation and the related issue of choke species is inter-species flexibility. In some instances, it appears that Member States are not using this tool to its full potential” (EU Commission, 2018). The NSAC advice states that the low usage of this measure is due to uncertainty regarding its impact on relative stability and on MSY.

Regarding a more long term view and the next reform of the CFP the need for a coherent results based management (RBM) or “output management” strategy across the policy and not just in relation to discards was expressed. This view was also reaffirmed by the Danish fisheries minister at the final DiscardLess conference in Copenhagen in January 2019. This RBM approach should be linked to EM as a control measure.

4. The LO in the North Western Waters: the Celtic Sea

Current situation

The Celtic Sea case study addresses demersal fisheries across most of ICES Area VII (excluding the Irish Sea VIIa and the Channel VIId-e). The main demersal species now subject to the LO in the region include: Nephrops, Cod, Megrim, Monk, Haddock, Whiting, Hake, Ling, Plaice, Pollock, Saithe and Common Sole. There are some exemptions in the Celtic Sea based either on high survivability or *de minimis*. Species covered by high survival exemptions (when fishing with certain gears) include nephrops, skates and rays and plaice. *De minimis* exemptions (again when fishing with certain gears) include whiting, black sole, cod, haddock, horse mackerel and mackerel. The main choke problems identified by the NWWAC in the Celtic Sea, which would persist even after all other measures have been applied, concern haddock and cod in ICES areas VIIb-k, sole in VIIf & g and plaice in VIIh,j & k (NWWAC, 2018).

Management approach taken

Since the LO was first implemented in demersal fisheries in 2016 the agreed approach by all Member States in the region was to avoid a “big bang” scenario in 2019 through the

progressive introduction of species and the use of catch thresholds. At the same time there was a progressively strong emphasis in the Joint Recommendations and subsequent Discard Plans between 2015 and 2018 on High Survival and *de minimis* exemptions. Member States with fleets active in the area initiated various selectivity trials but the uptake of more selective gears prior to 2019 has been relatively limited.

Across the diverse range of demersal fisheries in the area reported landings of unwanted catch, which would previously have been discarded, have been very low.

In Ireland, a fisheries program incentivising selective Nephrops fishery was introduced in 2018. In this program, vessels would be given an additional 20% of Nephrops quota in return for the use of more selective gears and commitments to take observers aboard and to provide economic data. Uptake rates for the scheme have been low, and it is not currently in operation. This may be due to the fact that Nephrops quotas are not as restrictive as many other demersal quotas for the Irish fleet.

Suggestions to move forward

The 2019 TAC and quota regulation contained a new approach to mitigating LO related choke problems whereby bycatch quotas were set for 5 stocks which had been subject to zero TAC advice by ICES. This approach has been broadly welcomed by the industry although some feel that the level of bycatch quotas set will only slightly delay choke related closures (Fishing News, 2018). Environmental NGO's and other interest groups involved in the NWWAC have set out specific conditions under which they could support any setting of TACs above the level advised by ICES (NWWAC, 2018, Annex II).

In Ireland, a new demersal quota balancing measure is being discussed in January 2019, which is aimed at providing some flexibility in order to mitigate against choke closures. The scheme provides for overshoots in a vessel's allocated monthly quotas where the vessel has to repay that overshoot from the following month's quota. Repayment tariffs are on a sliding scale with larger overshoots incurring higher repayment tariffs.

2019 also sees the introduction of a range of new technical measures in what is termed in the 2019 discard plan as the Celtic Sea Protection Zone (a subarea of the Celtic Sea which includes ICES VII f and g and part of VIIj)³. These measures provide for general increases in mesh size which can be offset to some extent if nets incorporate a range of specific selectivity measures which are linked to catch composition.

The NWWAC has identified three possible approaches to improve the LO implementation in the longer term, i.e. with potential application for the next CFP. These are: the use of "others" quotas (where a part of the overall TAC is set aside to cover catches by Member States without a specific quota allocation); footnotes to certain demersal TACs (these are footnotes in the TAC and quota regulation to allow for the counting of bycatches for no quota species, they are used already to allow for quantifying of bycatches in demersal fisheries of some pelagic and industrial species); and the temporary re-allocation of unused quota to cover bycatch (this would occur near the end of the year, after the calculations of the inter-annual quota flexibilities, to cover bycatch).

³ Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/2034 of 18 October 2018 establishing a discard plan for certain demersal fisheries in North-Western waters for the period 2019-2021.

5. The LO in South Western Waters: the Azores

Current situation

In the Azores bottom fisheries, the LO applied from January 2019. No changes in the way discards and unwanted catch are reported have been implemented by the Regional Government of Azores. However, the DiscardLess project has implemented an observer program to record discards practices in 2017 and 2018. No observer program is expected to run in 2019. The Regional Government requested *de minimis* exemptions for alfonsinos and greater forkbeard, and a survivability exemption for blackspot seabream for the hook-and-line fishery in ICES sub-area X. STECF considered that sufficient evidence was provided to demonstrate high selectivity, disproportionate costs and high socio-economic risks and supported these requests. They were approved by the European Commission (UE 2018/2033). It was later decided that the quota for greater forkbeard in area X should no longer be set due to very low catch amounts in the Azorean bottom longline fisheries, and that no fisheries directed to alfonsinos should occur, the quota remaining for bycatches only (UE 2018/2025).

For deep-water sharks, which were under a zero TAC since 2010, raising choke species concerns, it was finally decided in December 2018 by the European Commission to set a fishing prohibition on those species, meaning all individuals have to be released. A 10 t of bycatch allowance was granted to the drifting longline fishery targeting black scabbardfish as this bycatch was considered unavoidable (EC 2025/2018). Yet, regional management measures should be developed with a view to reducing bycatches of deep-sea sharks.

Blue jack mackerel, caught in the artisanal purse seine fishery in ICES zone X was also granted exemptions: i) *de minimis*: up to a maximum of 5 % in 2015 and 2016. Further, in 2017, 4 % of the total annual catches of horse mackerels may be discarded, and ii) survivability: all catches of jack mackerel may be released provided that the net was not fully taken on board (EU Reg. N° 1394/2014, EU Reg. N° 2018/188). An exemption was not requested for tunas as the tuna fishery in the Azores uses pole-and-lines that are highly selective and the fishery is managed by ICCAT. For swordfish, a derogation of the LO applies (Reg. EU 2015/98) with prohibition to keep and land <MLS swordfish, only an accidental catch of <MLS individuals of up to 15% of the total number of individuals can be kept and landed.

Current main issues

Interviews with fishermen performed in late 2016 suggest that most fishers were not aware of the LO regulations. Most of them fully disagree with the LO, stating that it does not make any sense, and is particularly inappropriate to the specificities of the outermost Region of the Azores and of their fisheries given that they would be forced to bring very small quantities of unwanted catches ashore in what are already very selective fisheries. Limited compliance can therefore be expected. Given the remoteness and extent of the archipelago, and the small-scale nature of the fisheries, enforcement would likely be difficult or ineffective.

Ways to further improve fishing selectivity appear limited. Fishers in the Azores are already using hook-and-line gears, which is one of the most selective fishing technique of European fisheries. Further, in recent years many longliners have been converted to

handliners, which are known to reduce unwanted catch and increase survival. Even if the EEZ is large, potential fishing grounds shallower than 800m depth are limited. Resources are perceived as largely mixed in all areas, making difficult to avoid specific areas to avoid unwanted catch.

For the unwanted catch that cannot be avoided, potential uses appear limited. Lack of land infrastructures and very high costs of collecting and processing this “non-valuable” catch can be expected. Lower compliance can be expected if this catch remains unused.

Suggestions for moving forward

In recent years, many longliners converted to handlining, mainly driven by regulatory and economic incentives. As a more active fishing technique (shorter soak times, greater flexibility, higher potential for survival, etc.) handlining appear as a promising mitigation measure better suited to avoid unwanted catch and improve post-release survival. Even if scientific knowledge regarding those questions has greatly improved in the recent years, in particular due to the DiscardLess project, further research would be necessary to have a more in-depth knowledge on both the resources and fisheries dynamics, and fishing selectivity. Continued monitoring through on-board observer programmes and scientific surveys should be pursued. Further at-sea fishing experiments should also be undertaken to test additional measures to avoid unwanted catch.

6. The LO in Mediterranean fisheries

Current situation

The Mediterranean case studies concern demersal fisheries from both the western (Balearic Islands and Gulf of Lion) and Eastern (Aegean Sea) basins. These areas encompass three different geographical subareas (GSAs), established by the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM) ⁴ for the assessment and management of Mediterranean stocks: i) Balearic Islands (GSA 5); ii) Gulf of Lions (GSA 7) and iii) Aegean Sea (GSA 22). The Landing Obligation in the Mediterranean applies to catches of species which are subject to Minimum Conservation Reference Sizes as defined in Annex III of Regulation (EC) N^o 1967/2006: a total of 20 fish species/groups, 4 crustaceans and 3 bivalve molluscs, which only represent a small fraction of the Mediterranean high species diversity with approximately 714 fish, 2,239 crustacean and 2,113 mollusc species. The application of this regulation was in accordance with the following time-frames: i) From 1st January 2015 for small and large pelagic species; and ii) from 1st January 2017 for species which define the fisheries and from 1st January 2019 for all other species in Mediterranean fisheries not covered by the previous point.

Management approach

Three High Level Groups (HLGs) of EU Member States were established in 2015 to develop regional management measures in the Mediterranean: the PESCAMED group (France, Italy & Spain), the Adriatica group (Croatia, Italy & Slovenia), and the SudEstMed group (Cyprus, Greece, Italy and Malta). The HLGs make Joint Recommendations (JRs) for discard plans following consultation with MEDAC (Mediterranean Advisory Council).

For small-pelagic species (anchovy, sardine, mackerels, horse mackerels) the EC adopted the Delegated Regulation (EU) 1392/2014 establishing a discard management plan for small pelagic fisheries in the Mediterranean. Since this management plan expired on 31 December 2017, the Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2018/161⁵ established a *de minimis* exemption to the LO for certain small pelagic fisheries and applies until 31 December 2020.

Regarding large pelagic fish, there is a derogation for bluefin tuna, as its management is regulated by the International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas (ICCAT). For the implementation of the ICCAT measures, the European Commission adopted the delegated Regulation 98/2015, according to which it is allowed to land and use for human consumption of up to 5% of undersized individuals of between 8 and 30 Kg, or length between 75 and 115 cm, by vessels targeting tuna and have fishing license for this. The same percentage is allowed as incidental catches by vessels not fishing actively bluefin tuna and having no fishing license.

In the case of demersal species, the EC adopted the Delegated Regulation (EU) 2017/86 establishing a discard management plan for certain demersal fisheries in the Mediterranean Sea applicable from 1st January 2017 until 31st December 2019. Different Articles of this Delegated Regulation were amended by the Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2018/153 following two joint recommendations submitted by the relevant Member States having a direct management interest and concerning the Western Mediterranean Sea and the Adriatic Sea. The demersal discard plan requires Member States to produce a list of vessels subject to the LO based on specified catch thresholds. In Spain, for example, the Ministry elaborated a list of vessels which are required to land all

⁴ www.gfcm.org

⁵ See: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32018R0161>

catches of Hake or Red Mullet based on the fact that more than 25% of their total catches in 2014 and 2015 were made up of these species.

Recently, a proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council⁶ resulted to a Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 2018/2036 of 18 October 2018 amending Delegated Regulation (EU) 2017/86 establishing a discard plan for certain demersal fisheries in the Mediterranean Sea⁷. This new Regulation provides for the extension until 31 December 2021 of the following exemptions already granted by Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 2017/86 as amended by Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 2018/153:

- survivability exemptions for scallop, carpet clams and Venus shells caught with mechanised dredges; and for Norway lobster caught with bottom trawls in the Western Mediterranean;
- *de minimis* exemption for hake and mullets caught with gillnets and trammel nets in the Western Mediterranean Sea, in the Adriatic Sea and in the South-eastern Mediterranean Sea; and for hake and mullets caught with 'rapido' (beam trawl) in the Adriatic.
- extended current survivability and *de minimis* exemptions for various single species.
- introduced new *de minimis* exemptions for some groups of species which cover the rest of the species in Annex III of Regulation (EC) No 1967/2006.

After the publication of Regulation (EU) 2015/812, the national Fishing Control Units informed all fishermen associations about the commitment of reporting discards data on the electronic fishing logbooks. The Fishermen Associations passed this information to their fleets but the Mediterranean Associations consulted do not know if discards are indeed reported on the logbooks because this depends directly on the Control Units.

Suggestions to move forward

Although the implementation of the LO is still mentioned as an objective, none of the proposed dispositions clearly improve its implementation. The implementation of catch quotas have been recently ruled out and even if selectivity improvement remains a useful tool, the proposal rather seem to hint toward effort management and temporary area closure in waters shallower than 100m (to limit unwanted catch during the earlier phase of whiting recruitment).

Regional actors in Mediterranean fisheries consider that the implementation of the LO would benefit from more fundamental changes in the longer term, i.e. with potential application for the next CFP. According to the MEDAC JR on Discard Management Plans (Ref. 132/2018)⁸, the landing of undersized fish products in Mediterranean fishing ports is not feasible. Accordingly, the main strategy should instead be to implement measures directed to reduce capture of unwanted catches. Considering the partial application of the LOs, the assessment of the situation in the various Member States and the ongoing projects for the improvement of gear selectivity, the MEDAC believes that periodically redefining the *de minimis* exemptions is the wrong strategy, even if it is based on new scientific evaluations. The *de minimis* exemptions will not produce any improvement in

⁶ See:

[http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/docs_autres_institutions/commission_europeenne/actes_delegues/2018/06718/COM_ADL\(2018\)06718_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/docs_autres_institutions/commission_europeenne/actes_delegues/2018/06718/COM_ADL(2018)06718_EN.pdf)

⁷ See: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/En/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018R2036>

⁸ See: http://www.med-ac.eu/files/documentazione_pareri_lettere/2018/05/132_medac_jr_lo_species_annexiii_regmed_en.pdf

the situation, on the contrary, it will increase bureaucracy and the on-board work required to register discards eligible for *de minimis* exemptions in the logbooks. Considering the general unfeasibility of processing fish products along the Mediterranean coastlines, for which no operational or economically feasible solutions appear to currently exist, the MEDAC considers that the requirement for the landing of undersized fish should be eliminated.

The STECF underlines that the exemptions requested by the recent joint recommendations cover a broad group of species with a wide range of discard rates and that specific information to fully support the exemptions requested have not yet been provided⁹. The Commission encourages Member States to increase the selectivity of the fishing gears in accordance with the results of current research programmes in order to reduce and limit unwanted catches and particularly catches below MCRS. It seems that the only way to move forward is to promote and incentivize the adoption of fishing technologies and practices that reduce pre-harvest mortality and post-harvest discards while avoiding damage to sensitive marine species and habitats¹⁰. The implementation of the LO mainly requires a change of the mentality and that is the most difficult part. Best practices and success stories where a win-win situation is highlighted must be widely presented to the fisheries Community in an effort to achieve cooperation with fishermen as well as actual implementation of the LO.

7. Update on the LO in the Baltic case study

Chapter 10 of the recent book on the LO contains a detailed account of the discarding situation in the Baltic Cod fishery (Valentinsson et al, 2019). The main points from the chapter are given below to provide an update on the situation outlined in the first DiscardLess Policy Brief (Fitzpatrick and Nielsen, 2016).

- Discarding rates of unwanted catches have not decreased since the implementation of the LO despite a reduced MCRS for Cod. There are some indications that discarding may have increased.
- Some of the discarding problem is linked to environmental conditions, reduced growth rates of cod and a negative economic situation for the fleet.
- Data quality for the Cod stock has not improved and may be worse since the LO. Recorded quantities of unwanted catches are “at least an order of magnitude lower than estimated volumes from independent estimates by scientific observer programmes and last haul inspections”. There are increased refusal rates for observers and there are concerns about observer effect and the representativeness of observer data.
- Gear selectivity has not improved since the introduction of the LO and may have been reduced due to gear manipulation (ICES 2017). The industry must be facilitated in their need to adapt gears to LO requirements.
- In order to move forward proper monitoring must be implemented to provide a real deterrent to discarding. On the other hand positive incentives should be used to encourage a mindset change such as preferential allocation of quotas to vessels

⁹ See:

[http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/docs_autres_institutions/commission_europeenne/actes_delegues/2018/06718/COM_ADL\(2018\)06718_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/docs_autres_institutions/commission_europeenne/actes_delegues/2018/06718/COM_ADL(2018)06718_EN.pdf)

¹⁰ Damalas et al, 2018. oi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.12681/mms.14195>

using more selective gears. Free gear choice should be used coupled with stronger requirement for documentation.

8. Cross Cutting Observations

8.1: Member state reports on LO implementation

STECF in the Spring 2018 plenary report (STECF, 2018) examined the reports received from MS and advisory councils providing detailed information on the impact of the landing obligation and national steps taken to assist with its implementation in 2017. 8 MS did not submit any report (Croatia, France, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Portugal, Romania or United Kingdom) and only 2 ACs responded to the request for information. The main conclusions of this assessment are listed below:

- Overall implementation of the transitional phase of the landing obligation has been challenging for MS and vessel operators.
- There is no evidence of significant changes in fishing practices and it is not possible to identify to what extent discard rates have been reduced.
- There was no data to allow a socio-economic impact assessment.
- No detected infringements of the landing obligation were reported but LO infringements are difficult to detect and prosecutions even more difficult to secure.
- Monitoring at sea needs to be increased significantly which can be achieved via alternative techniques including EM.
- The major weakness in monitoring of the LO is in reporting all catches so that the effects of changes in fishing practices can be identified.
- There is a lack of reporting by vessel operators of fish discarded under exemptions, discards of fish currently not subject to the LO and below MCRS catches.
- Observer coverage did not increase in 2017. In some MS there are indications that it had reduced due to increased refusal to take observers on board.
- Specific actions taken include numerous selectivity trials and compliance changes using risk-based and last haul approaches. There was limited usage of spatial measures, adjustments to quota management systems, and incentive schemes to encourage uptake of selective gears (in one MS).
- Very little information was provided on the outcomes of these specific actions so judgement of their effectiveness is not possible.

8.2 Points raised in the final DiscardLess conference

The DiscardLess project held a Science-Policy conference 30-31 January in Copenhagen with the title: “Landing Obligation 2019: What have we learned, what are the next steps?”. About 160 people attended, of which one third were project partners and two thirds were stakeholders from industry, environmental NGOs, researchers, and decision-makers at EU and national levels. In this section we summarise some of the observations and viewpoints expressed at the conference, with a focus on two plenary sessions.

In the first plenary session we looked back at the implementation of the LO from its initial application until today and discussed both positive and negative aspects of the LO. A total of 100 short statements were submitted electronically and despite some disagreements between some individual statements, there are also some clear commonalities. The main points are synthesised in relation to each of the questions raised below.

1) What are the positive aspects of the LO? What has worked?

The LO has been a driver for cooperation on all levels: within member states, between science and industry and through the regional management framework.

The LO stimulates innovation to address the discard issues and solve implementation problems.

The LO has led to improvements in selectivity, avoidance of areas with high levels of unwanted catches, and has increased knowledge on the survivability of discarded fish

The LO has created public awareness of the discard problem, and its implementation improves the image of the fisheries sector

The LO has led to a shift in mind-set: from enforcement of landings to enforcement of catches, and towards an ecosystem approach.

“It all takes time, this should be acknowledged, we are moving in the right direction”.

2) What are the main barriers for implementing the LO? What has not worked?

The LO came as a top down policy, and the communication with the industry has been insufficient - as a result it does not have the necessary buy-in from fishermen.

The LO is too complex, and the implementation period is too short.

The technical mitigation measures are inflexible, and it is difficult to get authorization to do one's own selectivity trials.

Control and enforcement of the LO is a big challenge.

There are insufficient facilities to handle unwanted catches, and the critical mass of unwanted catches to permit economically sustainable development of these facilities is not available.

Some fisheries will not be profitable under the landing obligation and more crew are needed.

The Mediterranean fishermen's perception is that the LO has been developed for TAC fisheries and it is difficult to apply in the Med.

Scientific knowledge is affected negatively due to changes in fishing patterns and unreliable discard data.

The LO has ecosystem impacts, not least for seabirds.

9. Discussion: The current state of the LO and future implementation

From the information presented here from case study reports, interviews and various correspondence there are a number of overarching questions which encapsulate the main issues with implementation of the Landing Obligation. In this section we provide a brief discussion of each and look at how progress may be made both in the medium and long term. We conclude with a discussion of how the problem of discarding in EU fisheries may be dealt with in the next CFP reform. Further aspects of these topics are discussed in other DiscardLess deliverable reports such as D4.4 and D7.4. We have focussed here on relatively brief discussions of how progress can be made on these issues in implementation of the LO.

Choke species

Few countries have implemented discard bans with chokes as a consequence or they have found flexibility tools which avoid regular fisheries closures due to choke situations (Karp et al 2019, LO Springer Book, Chapter 1). It is reasonable to state that under the LO choke problems have dominated the discussions and concerns, at least for mixed demersal fisheries outside of the Mediterranean. A number of the advisory councils have expressed concern that certain choke problems will persist even with full application of all of the available measures under Article 15. A number of reports on the implications of choke species problems in the North Sea, North Western waters and South Western waters have been commissioned by the European Parliament (Ulrich, 2018; Rihan, 2018; Prelezso, 2018).

The latest initiative used to try to address choke problems is the inclusion of bycatch quotas, along with mandatory bycatch reduction plans, in the 2019 TAC and quota regulation. While these bycatch quotas have been generally welcomed by industry, as they allow some flexibility and potential avoidance of choke closures, they are considered by others as a significant source of unsustainable fishing and increased fishing mortality on vulnerable stocks. Bridging the gap between these opposed viewpoints may depend on how seriously member states take the drafting of bycatch reduction plans, the monitoring of the plans implementation and the potential consequences or sanctions on fisheries which are benefitting from the availability of bycatch quotas. At the time of writing meetings are being held to discuss these issues and it remains to be seen whether this mechanism can be a workable and credible method of addressing the choke issue.

Monitoring

Although the issue of LO compliance was effectively deferred for 2 years this is becoming an increasingly important issue amid claims that current enforcement of the LO is insufficient and the tools available are inadequate (Borges et al, 2018; Plet-Hansen et al, 2017). Adequate enforcement and monitoring of the LO is important for a number of reasons: without it science will not have access to reliable data on discards; it is also needed in order to allow an assessment of sustainability in a fishery; and from a fishing industry perspective both potential increases in fishing mortality and consumer perceptions of illegal behaviour are risks to the viability of their enterprises.

The concept of Fully Documented Fisheries (FDF), where catches of relevant species are fully accounted for has been trialled in various EU fleets (Kindt-Larsen et al, 2011) and has been promoted as a potential solution to the LO enforcement problem (James et al, 2019). The most cost effective way to achieve FDF is through the use of EM, as the use of observers is both costly and problematic in terms of its reliability when assessing compliance with a discard ban.

The use of EM as a tool to monitor LO compliance is supported by the current proposal for a new EU fisheries control regulation (European Commission, 2018c) the current version of which specifies the use of cameras based on risk. Support for the use of this technology is particularly strong in some MS including Denmark and the UK. In a presentation to the final DiscardLess conference in Copenhagen in January 2019 the Danish Fisheries Minister outlined how EM will form the pillar of the Danish approach and expressed her view that it would allow for a general simplifying of regulations and a move towards a more results based management approach. Other interviewees involved in Danish fisheries policy discussions all confirm the emphasis on EM and cameras and support the moves towards electronic monitoring and results based management. One interviewee felt that Brexit could hasten the adoption of camera usage if access to UK waters is linked to camera use. A stronger emphasis on catch accounting through last haul analysis was also mentioned as an essential element in ensuring accountability at the vessel level (Schou, 2018).

The difficulty with implementing EM is that its use is not supported by large parts of industry and some MS have been less welcoming of it with some stating that it could create legal difficulties on vessels.

Incentivising the industry

The introduction of the LO was, notwithstanding a lengthy consultation process, a top-down measure precipitated by public and political pressure to act on addressing the problem of discards (Penas-Lado, 2016). The final iteration of the Landing Obligation, Article 15 of the 2013 CFP, was not the approach to discard reduction favoured by the industry (see Fitzpatrick et al, 2019 for a full discussion of this issue). Since the start of LO implementation in 2015 the DiscardLess project has collected data on stakeholder attitudes towards it and to date they have been largely negative (Frangoudes et al., 2019). This negativity is due largely to concerns that the policy will have a disproportionate economic impact on their activities and does not take into account their own efforts at reducing discards.

One of the main issues raised by the industry with the LO is the requirement to land which they consider an economic nonsense and involves wasteful killing of animals some of which may survive. This difficulty refers back to a problem with communicating what the main objective of the LO is because it involves two antagonistic perspectives, respectively those of “avoidance” and of “best use” of unwanted catches (van Hoof et al, 2019).

A change of focus from a landing obligation to a results based management approach or FDF may help to simplify communication about the purpose of the overall bycatch policy as this only requires fishers to ensure accountability regarding the mortality inflicted on the species in the catch, and thereby improve the management of target and bycatch species.

Catch quota management integrated with discard reductions programs, as Chile is moving to where discarding is allowed but accounted for in the quota and fisheries must demonstrate discard reduction initiatives (Karp et al, 2019) may be more acceptable to industry than the current system.

Removing the requirement to land may in some views remove a strong driver towards improvement in selectivity but a results based management approach with full catch accountability where permitted discards would be deducted from quotas would retain such a driver. The fact that industry are accepting of measures such as FDF and REM which would have been rejected previously is evidence that the LO is incentivising a change in mindset. It is likely that a pragmatic discard reduction approach with strong controls, clear targets and the support of industry will encourage further improvement than a policy that is overly reliant on control and with huge industry opposition.

Industry opposition to the LO presents a number of very significant barriers to its implementation and has wider implications for fisheries management. Non-compliance with the policy and an associated lack of real change in discarding patterns are an obvious risk. But on a broader scope deterioration in both scientific data on discards and the relationship between industry and science are emerging as significant outcomes of the LO at least currently (Valentinsson et al, 2019). There may also be a danger that fears regarding the use of industry provided data will subvert the desire among many fishers to tackle the problem.

Incentivising co-operative research and discard data provision will have many benefits including the stimulation of selective gear innovation by industry (Eliassen et al, 2019). This technical aspect of the LO at least can hopefully be addressed through the newly agreed technical measures regulation which should allow for more flexibility and responsiveness at a regional level in sanctioning the use of more selective gears.

Whether measures such as the incentivising of participation in fully documented fisheries through additional quota allocations are possible or will have the desired effect of improving industry attitudes towards the policy are debatable. This remains one of the most significant challenges which must be addressed in the next CFP reform.

Other current issues

Regionalisation: the evolution of the regionalised approach to EU fisheries governance continues with the gradual adoption of multi-annual plans and the recently agreed technical measures framework. How these mechanisms will interact with the Landing Obligation and also the newly required bycatch reduction plans is not fully apparent yet.

The LO has represented an important driver for the regional actors to test and use the regional approach. However, it is also clear that the regional process in many cases is in need of further development to be seen as an effective and legitimate policy process. The further implementation of the LO will depend on a consolidation of the regionalisation process, and there will definitely be an increased emphasis on the MS to act quickly and capacity building and human resource issues at MS level will have to be addressed in order for this element of governance to function effectively.

Consumer pressure: The loss of market access due to inability to demonstrate sustainability can be a complementary driver of change in fisheries along with regulatory requirements. This aspect is emerging in the discard issue also with the recent negative MSC assessment of the Eastern Baltic Cod fishery highlighting high discard rates and discrepancies in discard data. This is likely to be an issue for other EU fisheries seeking sustainability certification and the MSC hosted a seminar on the LO and MSC certified fisheries in December 2018 where it stated that it is “working with stakeholders to understand and prepare for this new EU law and ensure MSC certified fisheries can continue to be certified”¹¹. While certification drivers are not a substitute for the legislative process this additional driver can function as a useful spur to stimulate further LO implementation.

Timeline: The LO timeline is very ambitious when considering that it entailed a 180 degree turn from the previous situation where fishers were required to discard. It took much longer to establish discard bans and to get industry acceptance for them elsewhere (Karp et al, 2019). What we are starting to see in 2019 are reports from various MS of changes in behaviour such as additional control efforts, growing acceptance of the need for electronic monitoring, recording of discards in logbooks and small quantities of unwanted catches being landed (Pers. comm.) Although these reports are admittedly anecdotal and not supported presently by scientific data it may be that an accumulation of small changes is how the LO will proceed rather than through seismic changes. This is in line with Recommendation 3 in D7.4 which advises an incremental approach based on global experiences (Nielsen et al, 2018).

10. The EU’s discard policy – considerations for the next CFP reform

Many of the discard policies in place globally have been either gradually adapted e.g. Norway, Iceland, New Zealand or comprehensively redrafted e.g. Chile (Karp et al, 2019) and it is probable that some adaptations to the LO will be required in order to address some of the current implementation issues. In this concluding section we draw on feedback received from those involved in LO implementation and on global experiences to outline where some potential alterations could help to create an improved discard policy.

Various developments of the bycatch quota system contained in the 2019 TAC and Quota regulation could be considered. One approach could be a differentiated approach where species are designated either as primary or target species to which a discard ban applies or as secondary species which have a risk-based bycatch management approach applied to them. A similar approach to this is used in the Australian fisheries management system (Australian Government, 2018) and the possibility of applying such an approach was

¹¹ <https://www.msc.org/seminar-eu-landing-obligation>

discussed in correspondence between the NSAC and the Commission in 2017 (NSAC, 2017; Commission, 2017). Moving to a system such as this would involve some significant changes to the current CFP system, not least Article 15 and hence this is something that could only be considered under a CFP reform process. Another bycatch reduction measure which has not been applied in Europe and which may have potential to mitigate chokes is bycatch risk pooling (Little et al, 2015). Risk pools are privately managed but contractually binding rules which in fisheries are designed to minimize bycatches and ensure target fisheries remain open. They have significant elements of real-time spatial management which has not been a significant feature of EU fisheries management generally.

The fishing industry position on discards is also changing when compared to the common view held prior to the LO which favoured fishery specific discard plans but were not strong on the details of control (Fitzpatrick et al, 2019). When speaking to a number of fishing organisation representatives recently and drawing from statements made at the final DiscardLess conference in January 2019 a results based management position is emerging. This position accepts some form of FDF approach with the use of cameras being preferably linked to a risk assessment. The key issue in this position which differentiates it from the current LO is that it would allow full technical deregulation and the fisher is fully accountable for their catches. Below MCRS catches may or may not be landed but if they are not they will still be deducted from their quotas. Inherent in this position is an acceptance that certain fishing methods will have an unavoidable minimum level of discards and that such discards do not represent waste as they are quantifiable and recycled through the marine ecosystem. The RBM type approach inherent in this position obviously represents quite a departure from Article 15 and a number of other current aspects of the CFP.

One of the key questions going forward to the next CFP is whether an RBM approach incorporating EM has the potential to bridge the gap between industry interests and those who are looking for much stronger enforcement of the Landing Obligation. RBM would go well beyond the levels of deregulation and decentralisation evident in the recent evolution of a regionalised approach in the CFP. But its use could incentivise industry innovation and also improve scientific knowledge in fisheries.

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